

Reforms in Banking Sector in India

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Abstract

For the past three decades India's banking system has several outstanding achievements to its credit. It is no longer confined to only metropolitans or cosmopolitans in India. In fact, Indian banking system has reached even to the remote corners of the country. Since the process of liberalization and reform of the financial sector were introduced in 1991, banking sector has undergone major transformation. The underlying objectives of the reform were to make the banking system more competitive, productive and profitable. Indian banks especially the public sector banks and the old private sector banks are lagging far behind their competitors in terms of both productivity and profitability with the exception of the State Bank of India and its associates. The other public sector banks and old private sector banks need to go for the major transformation program for increase their productivity and profitability. After studying banking reform process it can be suggested that the public sector banks must create strategic alliance with the rural regional banks to open up rural branches and increased use of technology for improved products and services for the same.

Introduction

The first stage of reforms was shaped by the recommendations of the Committee on the Financial System (Narasimham Committee), which submitted its report in December 1991, suggesting reforms in banking, the government debt market, the stock markets, and in insurance, all aimed at producing a more efficient financial sector.

The Indian banking sector is an important constituent of the Indian financial system. The banking sector plays a vital role through promoting business in urban as well as in rural areas in recent years. Without a sound and effective banking system, India can not be considered as a healthy economy.

Indian banking sector has undergone major changes and reforms during economic reforms. Though it was a part of overall economic reforms, it has changed the very functioning of Indian banks. This reform have not only influenced the productivity and efficiency of many of the Indian Banks, but has left everlasting footprints on the working of the banking sector in India.

The basic objectives of financial sector reforms, that is efficiency, stability and financial deepening, have been largely fulfilled because of priority sector lending liberalisation, prudential framework and increased competition between nationalised banks and other banks.

Government of India appointed a high level committee headed by Shri M. Narsinham, a former governor of the reserve bank of India. Government of India set up two committees.

- Narsinham committee on financial sector reform in 1991.
- Narsinham committee on banking sector reform in 1998.

Governance Now 3rd India Banking Reforms Conclave 2018

Reforms is a journey, not a destination. With Hon’ble Prime Minister’s vision to make India a cashless economy, there is a need to bring changes in banks and the way banking is done, for the financial inclusion and smoother transition to the cashless regime.

Financial inclusion does not end at opening bank accounts. It is just a beginning of a multi-layered process. Financial inclusion itself is a process that encompasses the technology, tools, products and the understanding to use them to navigate the complexities of life

After the financial inclusion drive, demonetization has increased the financial transactions on those accounts. To discuss the reforms in banking from inclusion to transactions, and from agriculture to business, Governance Now India’s premier governance and public policy magazine from Sri Adhikari Brothers (SAB) group, is pleased to announce the third edition of India Banking Reforms Conclave. The conclave is scheduled to be held in September 2018 in Mumbai with the objective of creating a dialogue amongst Banks (public and private), Regulators, Academia, Economists and industry experts to generate insights into innovations and transformation in banks for furthering financial inclusion in the country.

Digital Innovation

- Transforming banking through digital innovations
- How regulations can trigger disruption and innovation
- Future of digital currency

Financial Inclusion

- Analysing major challenges in expanding Financial Inclusion and services across India
- Next phase of financial inclusion in the country

Reforms

- Strengthening Corporate Governance regulations and practices to bring reforms in the Banking sector
- How to deal with the impact of Economic fluctuation on Financial Institutions and Regulators
- Key reforms initiatives to spur performance and lower risks
- Emerging Regulatory and Supervisory issues in India with respect to fintechs.

Important Reforms in The Banking Sector in India

Reduced CRR and SLR

The Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) and Statutory Liquidity Ratio (SLR) are gradually reduced during the economic reforms period in India. By Law in India the CRR remains between 3-15% of the Net Demand and Time Liabilities. It is reduced from the earlier high level of 15% plus incremental CRR of 10% to current 4% level. Similarly, the SLR Is also reduced from early 38.5% to current minimum of 25% level. This has left more loanable funds with commercial banks, solving the liquidity problem.

Deregulation of Interest Rate

During the economics reforms period, interest rates of commercial banks were deregulated. Banks now enjoy freedom of fixing the lower and upper limit of interest on deposits. Interest rate slabs are reduced from Rs.20 Lakhs to just Rs. 2 Lakhs. Interest rates on the bank loans above Rs.2 lakhs are full decontrolled. These measures have resulted in more freedom to commercial banks in interest rate regime.

Fixing Prudential Norms

In order to induce professionalism in its operations, the RBI fixed prudential norms for commercial banks. It includes recognition of income sources. Classification of assets, provisions for bad debts, maintaining international standards in accounting practices, etc. It helped banks in reducing and restructuring Non-performing assets (NPAs).

Introduction of CRAR

Capital to Risk Weighted Asset Ratio (CRAR) was introduced in 1992. It resulted in an improvement in the capital position of commercial banks, all most all the banks in India has reached the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) above the statutory level of 9%.

Operational Autonomy

During the reforms period commercial banks enjoyed the operational freedom. If a bank satisfies the CAR then it gets freedom in opening new branches, upgrading the extension counters, closing down existing branches and they get liberal lending norms.

6. Banking Diversification : The Indian banking sector was well diversified, during the economic reforms period. Many of the banks have started new services and new products. Some of them have established subsidiaries in merchant banking, mutual funds, insurance, venture capital, etc which has led to diversified sources of income of them.

New Generation Banks

During the reforms period many new generation banks have successfully emerged on the financial horizon. Banks such as ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, UTI Bank have given a big challenge to the public sector banks leading to a greater degree of competition.

8. Improved Profitability and Efficiency : During the reform period, the productivity and efficiency of many commercial banks has improved. It has happened due to the reduced Non-performing loans, increased use of technology, more computerization and some other relevant measures adopted by the government.

Major Contours of The Financial Sector Reforms in India

- Removal of the erstwhile existing financial repression
- Creation of an efficient, productive and profitable financial sector
- Enabling the process of price discovery by the market determination of interest rates that improves allocative efficiency of resources
- Providing operational and functional autonomy to institutions
- Preparing the financial system for increasing international competition
- Opening the external sector in a calibrated manner; and
- Promoting financial stability in the wake of domestic and external shocks.

Future Role of The Development Banking

In the context of the emerging scenario of liberalisation and the financial sector reforms the development banks need to gear themselves to meet the varied requirements of the small and medium scale sector. They need to create new product that are relevant and impactful. In the new economic scenario, the role of technology has emerged as a strategic variable influencing manufacturing systems of the industrial units who need to reorient their strategies to meet the challenges of the competition. With the upward revision of the investment ceiling, much potential has now been created for technological upgradation and the vertical integration of the industrial units so as to derive advantage from economies of scale.

The liberalisation regime has also opened the doors for a large number of entrepreneurs to embark upon the setting up of venture with innovative technologies and their commercial applications with a high risk high return profile, which requires assistance through the venture capital route. Many development banks have, therefore, taken steps to provide sector specific Venture Capital funds to the small and the medium sectors. Various State Governments have already launched the Venture Capital fund scheme for the targetted sectors.

Another thrust area of the development bank is the marketing finance which hitherto the promoters had to bear. Marketing is the crucial area in the present competitive market and the development banks need to help the industrial units to market their product and/or encourage entrepreneurs to develop the common marketing infrastructure.

It has been suggested by the different industry associations to extend the merchant banking services to the small and medium scale units which hitherto were available mainly for the large scale units.

Conclusion

Banking sector in Indian has given a positive and encouraging responses to the financial sector reforms. Entry of new private banks and shaken up Public sector banks to competition. The financial sector reforms have brought India financial system closer to global standards. With the India increasingly getting integrated with the global financial world, the Indian banking sector has a still long way to go to catch up with their counter parts.